

PETROGRAPHY – PETRO CHEMISTRY OF PENINSULAR GNEISS FROM CHIGARGUNTA GOLD MINES, ANDHRAPRADESH

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Abstract:

The Chigargunta Gold Mine area is situated in the southern extension of Kolar Gold Fields. The area is very close to the tri junction of the state boundaries of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Tamilnadu. Petro graphic and Petro chemical analysis on Peninsular gneiss is illustrated.

Key words: *Fundamental Gneiss, Tectonic Forces, Cross hatched twinning, Migmatization, Metamorphism.*

INTRODUCTION

Peninsular gneiss one of the most common rock types of the study area. (Fig.1). The North-South trending Kolar schist belt is associated with peninsular gneiss. Foote (1889) named the gneiss as “Fundamental granitoid gneiss”. Later it was described as “Fundamental gneiss” by Smeeth (1916) and subsequently modified into “Peninsular gneiss”. Intrusion of granitic and pegmatitic veins are noticed within peninsular gneiss. The gneiss is found to range in composition from tonalite to granodiorite. Peninsular gneisses are generally migmatitic and heterogeneous in composition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The following is the literature survey for Petrographic and Petrochemical analysis on Peninsular gneiss.

Bailey, S.W, Bell, R.A. and Peng, C.J. (1958), Foote, R.B, (1989), Harker, A.(1909), Kohler, A. (1949), Smeeth, W.F, (1916), Suwa, K, (1956), Vernon, R.H. (1965),

OBJECTIVES

Study of Petrography and Petrochemistry of gneiss samples to assess the nature of Peninsular gneiss.

METHODOLOGY

On representative samples Mineralogical, Petrological and Petrochemical studies conducted following the Standard procedures in practice.

FINDINGS

PETROGRAPHY

Gneiss are fine to medium grained rocks exhibiting generally hypidiomorphic granular texture. The observed gneissosity may be due to the presence of biotite or hornblende which have parallel orientation along their longer axes. Megascopically, the gneisses are made up of quartz, K-feldspar, Plagioclase, biotite and minor hornblende. They are divided into

- i) Biotite – Granite gneiss;
- ii) Biotite – Hornblende - Granite gneiss;

Based on their mineral contents. The model composition is given in Table. 1.

MINERALOGY

Quartz: It is one of the essential constituents of the peninsular gneiss. It is usually fresh, devoid of inclusions, occupying the inter spaces between minerals. Quartz grains show the crushing effects. A big grain of quartz is seen often passing gradually at its borders to small crushed granules, each having a highly irregular margin. It exhibits undulose extinction, which is a result of stress (Bailey et al., 1958).

K-Feldspar: Potash feldspar is represented by microcline and is associated with plagioclase and Quartz. Microcline is reported in gneisses of Shivaganga and Shimoga areas also. On the basis of experimental proof, orthoclase, microcline and perhite are now regarded as different modifications of K-feldspars, containing a small amount of soda dissolved in it. The different forms assumed by these minerals are only functions of temperature like perhite at low temperature, orthoclase at high temperature and microcline at intermediate level. Microcline can be identified by its “cross – hatched twinning” (Fig. 2). The twinning differs in coarseness in the same grain at different portions. A combination of both fine and coarse grating in a single grain is common. The entire area of microcline may be characterized by grating or a portion of it may lack in it (Fig. 2). Albite and pericline twinning closely inter woven, gives a peculiar pattern, which is differently termed as “Cross-hatched”, “grid”, or “tartan patterns”. When viewed crossed nicols position in a direction approximately parallel to both the compositional planes, the cross – hatched intersections are seen to be nearly perpendicular to each other.

Many of the earlier workers have emphasized the importance of the stress or dynamic force in formation of microcline structure and some of the most salient and pertinent arguments are mentioned here under.

Harker (1909), points out that “the conversions of orthoclase to microcline” (Fig. 3). Or the setting up of the microcline structure in orthoclase has been attributed to dynamic forces.

Kohler (1949), found that the change from orthoclase to microcline form is aided by tectonic forces, which with increased intensity increase the coarseness of the exsolution of albite and produce microcline grating.

Microcline twinning is related to the different imperfections, some of which have been referred to as thermodynamically unstable imperfection. The continued deformational forces are responsible for cross-hatched twinning (Bailey et al., 1958).

Abundance of albite and pericline twins are attributed to the fact that require a small amount of sample shear parallel to their composition plane (Vernon, 1965).

From the aforesaid observations, it can be concluded that the rocks of the area under investigation must have been subjected to greater deformation.

Plagioclase: It occurs as sub-hedral grains. Majority of the grains are untwined. Lamellar or polysynthetic twinning is observed. Various twin laws exhibited by the feldspars of peninsular gneiss is given in Table. 2. The characteristic twin laws of igneous rocks are entirely absent. The twin laws of the feldspars, represented in Suwa (1956) diagram, fall in the metamorphic field. (Fig.4), hence the peninsular gneiss are metamorphic origin. The anorthite content varies from 20 to 30% and $2v = (-) 80^\circ - 85^\circ$.

Biotite: It is dominant ferromanesian mineral and mostly occurs in association with hornblende. It also occurs as elongated flakes and streaks. It is pleochroic showing $N_e = \text{Yellow}$ $N_v = N_z = \text{dark brown}$ and $(N_z - N_x) = 0.029 - 0.062$.

Hornblende: It occurs as elongate grains with their longer axes generally lie parallel to the gneissosity of the rock. They are associated with biotite. Alteration of hornblende and biotite is observed in some cases. It is pleochroic showing. X = Light yellow; Y = Yellowish green; Z = Dark yellowish green.

LIMITATIONS & CONCLUSIONS:

Petrochemistry:

Two representative samples are analysed and the data given in Table.3. The analysis of two gneisses indicate that they are of heterogeneous nature. Rock CP2 has higher SiO₂, Al₂O₂, TiO₂, FeO, Fe₂O, MgO, CaO and Na₂O than rock CP1. Where as HO is much lower in CP1 than CP2. Obviously CP1 has acquired higher K₂O during migmatization of CP2. The total alkalis being higher in CP1, the norm also shows only orthoclase, albite and no anorthite, and the entire Al₂O₂, is used up in the formation of orthoclase and albite and the CaO has gone for diopside. The model composition of the gneisses also show similar variation. This reflects variation in gneisses, and potash metamorphism played a role in the evaluation of the gneisses.

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Constituents	CP1	CP2
Quartz	21.05	25.10
K.Feldspar	59.00	55.20
Plagioclase	17.50	17.50
Pyroxene	---	---
Biotite	1.55	0.20
Olivine	---	---
Hornblende	---	1.50
Garnet	---	---
Sphene	---	---
Magnetite	0.90	0.50
Grunerite	---	---
Sillimanite	---	---
Muscovite	---	---
Pyrite	---	---

Table. 1. Model Analyses

Index:

CP1 : Biotite – Granite gneiss near Geological survey of India camp office.

CP2 : Biotite – Hornblende - Granite gneiss about 2 km SSW of Nandimadygu.

Table. 2. Frequency of twin laws in plagioclase feldspar

	Normal Laws		Parallel Laws		Complex Laws			Total Number of laws
	Albite	Manebach	Carlsbad	Pericline	Albite – Ala B	Albite - Carlsbad	Manebach – Ala	
CP1	4	---	---	---	4	---	---	8
CP2	5	---	2	---	6	---	---	13

Index:

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Table. 3: Chemical analysis and CIPW Norm

Constituents	CP1	CP2
SiO ₂	68.70	64.90
Al ₂ O ₃	15.44	15.64
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.39	1.90
FeO	2.31	2.50
MgO	1.20	2.25
CaO	1.30	4.15
MnO	0.04	0.06
Na ₂ O	1.90	2.50
K ₂ O	8.40	4.50
TiO ₂	0.30	0.90
P ₂ O ₅	0.20	0.20
H ₂ O	0.22	0.50
Total	100.30	100.30
CIPW Norm		
Quartz	22.38	20.94
Orthoclase	49.50	36.63
Albite	16.24	20.96
Anorthite	---	18.07
Corundum	---	---
Diopside	4.59	1.54
Hypersthene	3.63	6.58
Olivine	---	---
Magnetite	0.69	2.78
Ilmenite	0.61	1.67
Apatite	0.34	0.33

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